

VOL. 26, ISSUE 3

DECEMBER 2021

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Dear Colleagues and Friends,

As my presidency draws to a close, I wish to reflect upon our journey as a WGO community and share what we have accomplished together over these last few years.

It has been an honor to serve as President of the World Gastroenterology Organisation (WGO). When I started my presidency in September 2019, there were three main objectives that I wanted to achieve:

- Encourage more females to serve on WGO committees and participate in our initiatives;
- Attract more young physicians to participate in WGO programs and committees; and
- Increase our efforts towards growing our membership in Africa and other parts of the world.

With your support and collaboration, and despite the COVID-19 pandemic, together, we were able to achieve all of these goals. Below I share with you a summary about our various programs and what we were able to achieve together:

Nominations

WGO is committed to seeing a more diverse and inclusive GI community, dedicated to providing the highest standards in education, training and research in the field. We are working to ensure that there is balanced representation including, but not limited to, geographic, age, race and gender at both the committee and governance levels. In an effort to increase member participation, changes were made to the statutes and bylaws, decreasing the term limits, which would allow for members to join regularly.

Our nominations cycle for the 2021-2023 term had a record 155 applications received for our various committees and interest groups with all regions represented (Africa/Middle East, Americas, Asia-Pacific and Europe). The nomination of women increased significantly this cycle. We moved from less than 5% to 30% nominated to various committees and leadership positions, with 5 women appointed to the Governing Council for the 2021-2023 term. These numbers will continue to increase as we move forward.

IBD Mimickers in Tropical Countries

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The diagnosis of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) in tropical countries is often interfered by intestinal infectious diseases such as tuberculosis and amoebiasis. Both IBD and these infections have overlapping clinical manifestations and endoscopic findings. The differentiation between these conditions is important since the treatment for IBD, especially steroid or the biologic agents, will aggravate the infection.

Figure 1: A typical case of ileocecal involvement of tuberculosis. Endoscopic finding showed polypoid ulcerative lesion located at ileocecal area. The stool acid-fast bacilli was detected.

Tuberculosis (TB)

Intestinal tuberculosis comprised 10% of extrapulmonary tuberculosis, in which ileocecal areas are mostly involved.¹ Gastrointestinal infection is the consequence of direct ingestion of the pathogen in the pulmonary secretion, hematogenous spreading, direct inoculation from the adjacent organ,

or lymphatic spreading² but co-existent pulmonary lesion was found only in 15-47% of patients.^{2,3} TB usually appears as ulcerative or polypoid lesions (Figure 1) and the pathology showed granulomatous inflammation, which is difficult to distinguish from ileocecal Crohn's disease⁴ (Table 1, Figure 2A, 2B and 2C). The diagnosis of intestinal tuberculosis mainly depends on tissue diagnosis, in which the positive acid-fast bacilli could be identified in only 10%.³ When using tissue PCR for TB, the sensitivity increased to 47%, and specificity increased to 95%.⁵ The result could be improved using Xpert MTB/RIF assay in biopsy tissue with 32-33% sensitivity and 100% specificity.^{6,7} When using the interferon- γ release assay, the sensitivity could be improved up to 86% with 93% specificity.³ The differentiation between these two diseases is important since most of the treatment for Crohn's disease would aggravate tuberculosis. In the

	Crohn's disease	Tuberculosis
Clinical feature	male gender hematochezia perianal disease intestinal obstruction extraintestinal manifestations	fever night sweats lung involvement ascites
Endoscopic feature	longitudinal ulcers cobblestone appearance luminal stricture mucosal bridge rectal involvement perianal disease	transverse ulcers rodent-like ulcers patulous ileocecal valve cecal involvement
Pathology	focally enhanced colitis	confluent submucosal granulomas lymphocyte cuffing ulcers lined by histiocytes
Cross-sectional imaging	asymmetrical wall thickening left sided colonic involvement intestinal wall stratification comb sign fibrofatty proliferation abscess	short segmental involvement lymph nodes along right colic artery lymph nodes with central necrosis contracture of ileocecal valve fixed patulous ileocecal valve

Table 1 Features suggestive of ileocecal Crohn's disease or tuberculosis^{4, 19, 20}

Figure 2: An atypical case of intestinal TB in 26 years old male with single terminal ileal ulcer (A), pathological findings showed epithelioid cells granulomas and Langhans giant cells by H&E staining (B: 10x magnification, C: 100x magnification).

high prevalent areas, extensive screening for active or latent tuberculosis is warranted prior to the initiation or during biologics or immunosuppressive therapy. In case that active or latent TB were detected, treatment for TB should be considered for at least three weeks prior to the initiation of anti-TNF.⁸

Amoebiasis

Intestinal amoebiasis is an infectious disease caused by the protozoa *Entamoeba histolytica*. This protozoan is transmitted by ingestion of the cyst, and colitis occurs when trophozoite penetrates intestinal mucosa.⁹ The clinical presentation of patients with amoebic colitis included abdominal pain, fever, and watery or bloody diarrhea which can last for several weeks. In some cases, acute necrotizing colitis or perianal ulceration and fistula formation could be found.⁹ The endoscopic findings of amoebic colitis included discrete small ulcers less than 2 cm in diameter in the cecum or rectosigmoid, with intervening normal mucosa¹⁰ and ulcers with exudate. The combination of cecal lesions, multiple lesions, and exudates is highly suggestive for amoebic colitis.¹¹ The diagnosis for amoebic colitis could be done based on the detection of *E histolytica* in the stool or antigen detection in the serology. However, stool examination lack specificity for the diagnosis of *E histolytica* against

other nonpathogenic species, with only 50-60% sensitivity.¹² The colonic biopsy specimen usually showed diffuse colitis in variable severity, but classical flask-shape lesion is rarely seen.⁹ The amoeba usually identified in the mucinous exudates and the trophozoite could be seen in 88% of the direct smear of intestinal washing.¹³ In cases that amoebiasis was misdiagnosed as IBD, life-threatening fulminant colitis after steroid administration was reported.¹² Therefore, in endemic regions, various diagnoses to exclude amoebiasis should be made before the treatment of IBD.

Strongyloidiasis

Strongyloidiasis is the infection caused by *Strongyloides stercoralis*. This parasite is soil-transmitted and infested by penetrating the intact skin of the host. Gastrointestinal manifestation of strongyloidiasis included abdominal pain, diarrhea, protein-losing enteropathy, or constipation.¹⁴ Endoscopic findings of gastroduodenal involvement showed mucosal edema and erythema, while colonoscopy might show mucosa with loss of vascular pattern, edema, aphthous ulcers, erosions, serpiginous ulcerations, and xanthoma-like lesions.¹⁵ The histology specimen showed edema of lamina propria with infiltration with lymphocyte, plasma cells, and eosinophils, which might overlap with IBD.¹⁶ The definite diagnosis of this condition

is the identification of *Strongyloides* larvae in the specimen. Misdiagnosis of strongyloidiasis as IBD can result in devastated outcome since the use of corticosteroid may lead to life-threatening strongyloidiasis hyper-infection syndrome.¹⁷ As a result, in any guideline, screening, or empirical treatment using ivermectin in patients who need corticosteroid is recommended.¹⁸

In summary, there are several infectious diseases that can mimic IBD. The differential diagnosis between intestinal TB and colonic Crohn's disease depends on clinical findings and endoscopic tissue testing. Amoebic colitis could present with inflammation and ulceration, but the identification could be made by pathological findings and direct smear. Patients with strongyloidiasis might have similar clinical and endoscopic manifestation as IBD, but the diagnosis can be made bases on histological examination. In the particular cases which IBD and its infectious mimickers are not distinguishable, especially with atypical manifestation, therapeutic trial with anti-infection regimens prior to the immunosuppressive therapy seems to be a safer approach.

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